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Comparative Effects of Set-Induction and Demonstration Approaches on Basic Education Students' Interest in Algebra in Umuahia-North Local Government Area, Abia State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored the comparative effects of set-induction and demonstration approaches on the interest of Upper Basic Education students in algebra in Umuahia-North Local Government Area, Abia State, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design involving non-equivalent groups was adopted. The sample comprised 159 Basic 7 students, including 94 males and 65 females. Two intact classes were exposed to the set-induction approach, while the other two were taught using the demonstration approach. Instruction followed the regular school timetable. The data collection instrument was the Algebra Interest Inventory (AII), which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.92, indicating high reliability. The study addressed three research questions and tested three hypotheses. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

Findings indicated that students taught with the demonstration approach had higher mean interest ratings compared to those taught using the set-induction approach, with a statistically significant difference ($F_{(1,158)} = 6.04, p = 0.015$). Furthermore, female students taught with the set-induction approach showed greater interest than their male counterparts. Similarly, among students taught using the demonstration approach, females had higher mean interest ratings than males, although this difference was not statistically significant. The study concluded that the demonstration approach was more effective in enhancing students' interest in algebra. It was recommended that mathematics educators integrate both set-induction and demonstration approach to foster active participation and bridge gender-related interest gaps in algebra.

Keywords: Mathematics, Mathematics Education, Set-Induction Approach, Demonstration Approach, Interest, Algebra, Basic Education

Introduction

Mathematical proficiency is essential for both individuals and nations, influencing everyday transactions, scientific exploration, technological innovation, and effective problem-solving. As emphasized by Akinoso (2011), mathematics underpins science and technology and serves as a fundamental tool for national development. Its importance to student success and nation-building underscores its central role in both general and science-focused education.

According to Ayeni (2011), teaching aims to bring about positive changes in learners to achieve specific educational goals. Therefore, effective teaching must adopt suitable instructional strategies that facilitate these intended transformations. Teachers, as facilitators of learning, must adopt methods that actively engage and motivate learners. Abdolreza *et al.* (2017) observed a noticeable decline in academic performance among Nigerian students across all educational levels in recent decades. The Basic Education curriculum emphasizes the need for effective teaching strategies tailored to students' needs. This calls for dynamic, innovative instructional methods that can boost students' interest in mathematics, particularly in algebra.

Mathematics education fosters students' capacity for analytical reasoning, both symbolic and quantitative, and emphasizes strong subject-matter understanding alongside effective instructional techniques (Iji & Abah, 2018). Given that teaching is a continuous process aimed at achieving learning outcomes, educators must adopt methods that align with learners' needs. Bharadwaj and Pal (2011) highlighted the importance of selecting instructional approaches that accommodate students' unique ways of processing information. Teachers must use methods that align with specific learning objectives and spark student interest, thereby making mathematics more engaging.

Research has shown that teaching quality directly affects students' interest in learning. Adunola (2011) stressed the importance of using diverse teaching strategies, particularly for complex concepts. Many studies have linked declining student achievement in mathematics to poor instructional practices and ineffective teaching materials (Etukudo, 2016; Salau, 2013). This has led to growing concerns from parents and stakeholders about the quality of mathematics instruction in Nigerian schools (WAEC, 2018). The set-induction approach is often used at the beginning of a lesson to establish a cognitive and emotional framework that prepares students for learning (Hargie, 2016). Also referred to as the "interest

approach”, it uses various strategies to capture students’ attention and transition them into the learning mindset (Oman, 2012). This approach bridges the gap between learners’ experiences and the lesson’s goals, helping them connect new content to prior knowledge. Research by Hargie (2016) found that students taught by teachers trained in set-induction methods showed greater engagement and academic performance than their peers.

The demonstration approach combines verbal explanation with hands-on manipulation of objects, tools, or visual aids to convey concepts (Akinbobola & Ikitde, 2011). It contextualizes mathematical content through real-life applications and promotes active student engagement. Giridharan and Raju (2016) noted that demonstrations enhance memory retention and encourage interaction between students and teachers. This method supports experiential learning by involving students in observing, questioning, and responding in real time. Interest plays a crucial role in learning outcomes. Obodo (2012) described it as a compelling internal force that motivates a learner to engage with a stimulus.

When students find a topic appealing, they are more likely to participate actively and retain information. Harbor-Peters (2012) emphasized that interest cannot be imposed; rather, it arises naturally when learners are curious and engaged. Despite its importance, algebra remains a difficult area for many students. Mastering algebra often requires integrating multiple concepts, which can be challenging for students transitioning from arithmetic thinking (Witzel, Mercer, & Miller, 2013; Malara, 2013). Research shows that many students struggle with basic algebraic concepts due to a lack of foundational understanding (Warren & Cooper, 2013). The National Council of Teachers of Mathematics - NCTM (2000) recommends using pattern recognition and generalization activities in the early grades to build algebraic thinking. Another factor influencing student interest in algebra is gender. The Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency (2016) observed that boys tend to perform better in quantitative subjects, while girls often lack confidence in mathematics. Similarly, Harbor-Peters (2013) found that gender disparities persist in mathematics achievement. These differences may stem from variations in interest and engagement rather than ability alone (Jensen & Owen, 2012). Given these challenges, it is essential to explore instructional methods that not only improve understanding but also boost interest – especially in algebra. This study, therefore, investigates the comparative effectiveness of set-induction and demonstration approaches in fostering students’ interest in algebra at the Upper Basic Education level in Umuahia-North Local Government Area of Abia State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to find out the comparative effects of set induction and demonstration approaches on basic 7 students’ interest in algebra. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. determine the comparative effects of set-induction and demonstration approaches on Upper Basic 7 students’ interest in algebra.
- ii. determine the effects of set-induction approach on Upper Basic 7 males and female students’ interest in algebra.
- iii. determine the effects of demonstration approach on Upper Basic 7 male and female students’ interest in algebra.

Research Questions

To carry out the study the following research questions were asked to guide the study:

- i. what are the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 students taught algebra using set-induction and demonstration approaches?
- ii. what are the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using set-induction approach?
- iii. what are the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using demonstration approach?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference in the mean interest rating of Upper Basic 7 students taught algebra using set-induction and demonstration approaches.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the mean interest rating of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using set-induction approach.
- iii. There is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using demonstration approach.

Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design, specifically a non-randomized, pre-test and post-test design involving non-equivalent groups. The target population consisted of all 44,718 Upper Basic students enrolled in the 17 government-approved secondary schools within Umuahia North Local Government Area, Abia State, Nigeria, during the 2018/2019 academic session. This population included 23,047 male and 21,671 female students (SEMB, 2018/2019). From this population, a sample of 159 students was selected using purposive sampling. Four secondary schools were chosen, with two schools assigned to the set-induction approach and the other two to the demonstration approach. In the schools using set-induction, intact classes consisted of 12 males and 10 females in one, and 30 males and 25 females in the other. Similarly, in the schools using the demonstration method, intact classes had 15 males and 8 females in one, and 37 males and 22 females in the other. The primary instrument for data collection was the Algebra Interest Inventory (AII), which comprised 44 items measured on a 4-point Likert scale. This tool was validated by three subject matter experts to ensure content accuracy and clarity. To determine the reliability of the instrument, the researchers conducted a pilot test with 20 Upper Basic 7 students from a school in the same area. The AII yielded a Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.92, indicating a high level of internal consistency. The researchers administered the instrument with the support of the participating schools' mathematics teachers. It was distributed to the 159 selected students across the four sampled schools, and all complete questionnaires were collected immediately to avoid data loss. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to answer the research questions. The Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to test the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. This method helped account for any initial

differences between the groups and determined the true effect of the teaching approaches on students' interest in algebra.

Results

Results of this study were presented according to the research questions and followed with related hypotheses.

Research Question One

What are the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 students taught algebra using set-induction and demonstration approaches?

TABLE 1: The Mean interest ratings and Standard Deviation of Upper Basic 7 students taught algebra using Set-induction approach and Demonstration approach.

Group		N	Mean	SD	Mean Diff
Set-Induction	Pre-Rating	77	2.67	0.28	0.36
	Post-Rating	77	3.03	0.31	
Demonstration	Pre-Rating	82	2.56	0.29	0.58
	Post-Rating	82	3.14	0.30	
Total		159			

In Table 1, the mean interest ratings of students taught algebra using Set-induction approach with pre-interest ratings and post-interest ratings are 2.67 and 3.03 respectively with the standard deviation of 0.28 and 0.31 for Set-induction approaches. Also in Table 1, the mean interest ratings of demonstration approach for pre-interest ratings and post-interest ratings are 2.56 and 3.14 respectively with the standard deviation of 0.29 and 0.30 for demonstration approach indicating that the approaches had effects on the student's interest. The mean difference of Upper Basic 7 students pre-interest rating and the post-interest ratings taught algebra using set induction approach is 0.36 and demonstration approach 0.58 with demonstration having higher mean difference.

Research Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean interest rating of Upper Basic 7 students taught algebra using set-induction and demonstration approaches.

TABLE 2: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on pre-interest ratings and post-interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 students taught algebra using set-induction and demonstration approach.

SOURCE	Type III Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	p - value	Remark
Corrected Model	.681 ^a	2	.340	3.722	.026	
Intercept	14.000	1	14.000	153.080	.000	
PRE-RATING	.235	1	.235	2.568	.111	
GROUPS	.553	1	.553	6.042	.015	Significant

Error	14.267	156 .091
Total	1532.585	159
Corrected Total	14.948	158

a. R Squared = .046 (Adjusted R Squared = .033), $p < 0.05$

In Table 2, $F_{(1,158)} = 6.042$ with p-value of 0.015 which is less than the stated 0.05 level of significance. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 students taught algebra using Set-induction and Demonstration approaches. We therefore conclude that both teaching approaches improve the interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 students in algebra using Set-induction and Demonstration approaches.

Research Question Two

what are the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using set-induction approach?

TABLE 3: The mean interest ratings and standard deviation of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using Set-induction approach

Group	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Mean Diff
Pre-Interest Ratings	Male	42	2.54	0.27	0.58
Post-Interest Ratings	Male		3.12	0.29	
Pre-Interest Ratings	Female	35	2.53	0.32	0.59
Post-Interest Ratings	Female		3.12	0.30	
Total		77			

Table 3 shows the mean interest ratings of male and female upper Basic 7 students taught algebra using Set-induction approach. For the pre-interest rating and post-interest ratings, the means are 2.54 and 3.12 respectively with the standard deviation of 0.27 and 0.29 for male students which indicate set-induction approach had enhanced their interest on the students. Also in Table 3, the pre-interest ratings and post-interest ratings for female students are 2.53 and 3.12 respectively with the standard deviation of 0.32 and 0.30 indicating set-induction approach had enhanced female students' interest in algebra. The mean difference of the male students' pre-rating and post-interest ratings is 0.58 while that of the female students is 0.59, indicating that the female students have a slightly higher mean rating than the male students.

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean interest rating of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using set-induction approach.

TABLE 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on pre-interest ratings and post-interest ratings for male and female students taught Algebra using set-induction approach

Source	Type III Sum Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	p - value	Remarks
Corrected Model	.678 ^a	2	.339	3.822	.026	
Intercept	3.944	1	3.944	44.434	.000	
PRE-RATING	.678	1	.678	7.643	.007	
GENDER	.000	1	.000	.003	.956	Not Significant
Error	6.569	74	.089			
Total	716.432	77				
Corrected Total	7.248	76				

a. R Squared = .094 (Adjusted R Squared = .069), p > 0.05

In Table 4, $F_{(1,76)} = 0.003$ with p-value of 0.956 which is greater than the stated 0.05 level of significance. This means that the null hypothesis is accepted this implies that there is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using set-induction approach.

Research Question Three

What are the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using demonstration approach?

TABLE 5: The mean interest ratings and standard deviation of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using Demonstration approach

Group	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Mean Diff
Pre-Interest Ratings	Male	52	2.58	0.27	0.55
Post-Interest Ratings	Male		3.13	0.29	
Pre-Interest Ratings	Female	30	2.53	0.32	0.64
Post-Interest Ratings	Female		3.17	0.30	
Total		82			

Table 5 shows the mean interest ratings of male and female upper Basic 7 students taught algebra using demonstration approach. For the male students, the pre-interest rating and post-interest ratings means are 2.58 and 3.13 respectively with standard deviations of 0.27 and 0.29 while for the female students, the pre-interest ratings and post-interest ratings are 2.53 and 3.17 respectively with standard deviations of 0.32 and 0.30 indicating that

demonstration enhanced students' interest in algebra. The mean difference of the male students is 0.55 while that of female students is 0.64, which indicates that with the demonstration approach the female students obtained a higher mean interest rating than the male students.

Research Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using demonstration approach.

TABLE 6: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on pre-interest ratings and post-interest ratings of male and female students taught Algebra using demonstration approach.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	p - value	Remarks
Corrected Model	.042 ^a	2	.021	.229	.796	
Intercept	10.741	1	10.741	117.638	.000	
PRE-RATING	.010	1	.010	.111	.740	
GENDER	.029	1	.029	.315	.577	Not Significant
Error	7.213	79	.091			
Total	816.153	82				
Corrected Total	7.255	81				

a. R Squared = .006 (Adjusted R Squared = -.019) P > 0.05

In Table 6, $F_{(1,76)} = 0.315$ with p-value of 0.577 which is greater than the stated 0.05 level of significance. This means that the null hypothesis is accepted, implying that there is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings of Upper Basic 7 male and female students taught algebra using demonstration approach.

Discussion

The findings in Table 1 revealed that students who were taught algebra through the demonstration approach had higher mean interest ratings than those taught using the set-induction approach. Furthermore, Table 2 indicated a statistically significant difference in the interest levels of students taught using both approaches, highlighting the superior effectiveness of the demonstration approach in fostering interest in algebra. These findings are consistent with Daluba (2013) who emphasized that maintaining and enhancing students' interest in algebra requires teachers to actively engage learners in well-organized class activities. Teachers should be ready to re-demonstrate concepts when students fail to grasp them initially and integrate relevant instructional materials to support learning.

From Table 3, female students taught with the set-induction approach recorded higher mean interest rating than their male counterparts; however, this difference was not statistically significant as shown in Table 4. Nevertheless, the set-induction approach has the potential to reduce gender disparities in students' interest in algebra. This aligns with the observations of Unodiaku (2012) and Goolsby (2013) who identified lack of interest as a contributing factor to poor academic performance in mathematics. Similarly, the findings support Bharadwaj and Pal (2011) who advocated the use of suitable instructional approach that aligns with learning goals and stimulates students' interest. Table 5 showed that female students also had higher mean interest ratings than males when taught using the demonstration approach. However, Table 6 revealed that this gender difference was not statistically significant. This suggests that the demonstration approach can also help close gender gaps in students' interest in algebra. These results corroborate the findings of Ochogba *et al.* (2019), who reported that students taught through the demonstration approach outperformed those taught with alternative approaches. The findings are also in line with Rebecca and Angela (2012) and Adegbola (2019) who affirmed that demonstration approach enhance students' interest in learning.

Conclusion

This study concludes that students taught algebra using the demonstration approach exhibited higher interest levels than those taught with the set-induction approach. Given the significant difference observed in their mean interest rating, it can be inferred that while both approaches positively influence student interest, the demonstration approach may be more effective in stimulating and sustaining engagement in algebra. It is therefore recommended that mathematics teachers incorporate both set-induction and demonstration approaches into their instructional practices. These approaches promote active participation from both teachers and learners, enhance student engagement, and may help reduce gender-based interest disparities. Overall, the integration of these approaches in mathematics instruction could significantly improve students' interest.

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